

**Outcomes in long-term follow up of sporadic Parkinson's disease in the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative
Code Sharing README file**

Table of Contents

1. Introduction
2. Software
3. Employed Datasets
4. File Instructions
5. Acknowledgements
6. Disclaimer

1. Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide guidance to assist a third-party researcher in understanding the organization and presentation of the statistical analysis code included in the Zenodo folder [10.5281/zenodo.20414904].

The shared code was created to perform analyses for the published article, "Outcomes in long-term follow up of sporadic Parkinson's disease in the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative" [https://doi.org/10.1002/ana.78248]. This code was created to analyze data accessed from the PPMI database (RRID:SCR_006431) on June 24, 2024. As the PPMI database is always evolving, it is possible that the code may not work if the database has changed since the date the code was created.

Analytic datasets are not included in the submission. Researchers can request access to PPMI data at the PPMI Study website (<https://www.ppmi-info.org/access-data-specimens/download-data>).

2. Software

All shared codes were written using SAS 9.4.

3. Employed Datasets

The shared code references the following datasets:

- advanced_pd_v7_24jun2024 – contains visit-level data on all participants
- advanced_pd_tte_v5_24jun2024 – contains subject-level survival data on all participants

4. File Instructions

The following files are included with the submission:

- 1) Table 1 – baseline demographic and clinical characteristics (04/03/26)
- 2) Tables 2, 3, and S1 – longitudinal demographic, clinical, imaging, and biomarker characteristics (04/03/26)
- 3) Figure 1 – NSD stage by annual visit (04/23/26)
- 4) Tables S2a, S2b, Figures 2 and 3 – survival analysis results (04/23/26)
- 5) Table Macros – (04/03/26)

4.1 Table 1

Derives baseline descriptive statistics and p-values across baseline stages for demographic and clinical characteristics in Table 1.

4.2 Tables 2, 3, and S1

Derives longitudinal descriptive statistics for demographic, clinical, imaging, and biomarker characteristics in Tables 2, 3, and S1.

4.3 Figure 1

Derives stacked bar chart of NSD stage by annual visit in Figure 1.

4.4 Tables S2a, S2b, Figures 2 and 3

Derives raw output used to generate hazards ratios and p-values shown in tables S2a and S2b, as well as the adjusted survival functions presented Figures 2 and 3.

4.5 Table Macros

Contains the Macro functions employed in SAS codes 4.1 and 4.2.

5. Acknowledgements

Codes are shared in compliance with the open access policy for Aligning Science Across Parkinson's (ASAP) (<https://parkinsonsroadmap.org/open-access-policy/>).

6. Disclaimer

Manuscript authors will not provide assistance in the use of the shared code. If a potential error is found in the shared code, please contact the lead author.